

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ACCOUNTING ADDITIONAL FUNDS
OUTSIDE THE BUDGET IN THE INSTITUTIONS OF THE PUBLIC EDUCATION
SYSTEM.

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Introduction. In the economy, the financing of public budget organizations is mainly carried out from the state budget and off-budget funds. The targeted and specific expenditure of budget and off-budget funds in budget organizations is directly related to the effective organization of their accounting, the transparency of financial reporting indicators, and the organization of their control. For this reason, great attention is being paid in many countries around the world to organizing budget execution accounting and reporting based on the requirements of international standards for accounting in the public sector.

The processes of studying research indicate that a number of scientific studies have been conducted aimed at adapting the methodology of budget execution accounting and reporting in budget organizations to international standards in international practice. In these scientific research works, issues such as the budget system and its management, organizing budget execution accounting, maintaining accounts, and preparing reports have found their solutions based on the cash and accrual methods of accounting, as well as improving the information support of budget reporting. However, issues related to organizing the methodology of accounting for budget and extra-budgetary funds in institutions of the national education system to the level of international accounting standards and increasing the transparency of budget report information remain vague.

It should be emphasized that consistent work is being carried out to expand the use of economic and financial statistical data in the framework of reforming the sectors of our country's economy and to introduce new mechanisms to increase the transparency of the budget process. In order to further enhance the openness and transparency of budget data and strengthen the control over the formation and expenditure of budgetary funds, according to the Resolution No. 506 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 24, 2020, on the "Strategy for Improving the State Financial Management System of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2024", the standardization of budget accounting, the improvement of the internal control and audit system, and the strengthening of financial discipline are being implemented, ensuring the transparency, completeness, and compliance of information with international standards, strengthening parliamentary and public oversight over the budget process, increasing accountability for the expenditure of funds within the budget system, and expanding the application of modern information systems in the budget execution process are required. In turn, these aspects demand a thorough investigation and improvement of the existing methodological foundations regarding the accounting and reporting of extrabudgetary funds in the institutions of the public education system.

Literature review. Various opinions and perspectives have been expressed by economist scholars and specialists regarding the concept of budget and extra-budgetary funds in budget organizations, the conduct of accounting, and the organization of budget control. Among them, economist scholars from our republic, such as A. Ibragimov, S. Mehmонов, B. Sugurbayev, A. Ostonkulov, and foreign

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economist scholars like S. Beglova, A. Zatova, O. Kolevatova, have conducted research. In particular, the manual written by K. Ibragimov and B.

Sugurbayev states that 'In budget organizations, the aim is to study, control, and manage the movement and status of budgets and extra-budgetary funds allocated within the limits of income and expenditure estimates of the organization, establish a system for forming information related to the execution of the budget, and provide users (internal, external) with information.

In S.U. Mehmohonov's scientific research, the issues of improving the methodology of accounting and internal audit in budget organizations have been studied.

Economist scholar A. Ostonkulov emphasized the necessity of ensuring that extra-budgetary funds of budget organizations are spent for the purposes stipulated in the budget, and that in cases where additional funding sources are available, expenditures should be planned to increase relative to the budget.

Foreign scholars S. Beglova, A. Zatova, and O. Kolevatova have researched the peculiarities of organizing accounting and control over the execution of budgets based on their funding sources in budget organizations.

As a result of scientific research conducted on improving the theoretical and methodological foundations of budgetary organizations' extrabudgetary funds accounting and reporting, a number of scientific results have been obtained, including the refinement of cash and accrual methods of budget accounting and reporting based on international accounting standards. In particular, methodological recommendations have been developed for ensuring the transparency of information on extrabudgetary funds in budget systems for both developed and developing countries, establishing a strong internal control environment in budget management, and implementing international accounting standards to ensure accountability and transparency of information. It has been proven that in the context of global crisis, the reliability of accounting information on the expenditure of budget organizations' funds contributes to the financial stability of nations.».

Analysis and results. In the conditions of a market economy, budget organizations have the right to receive additional income from sources other than budget funding. The full allocation of these additional funds to the off-budget accounts of budget organizations and the increase of budget organizations' employees' interests in utilizing these funds encourage the extensive use of property linked to budget organizations and other opportunities of budget organizations, provides additional momentum for economic growth, and expands opportunities for further development of entrepreneurship.

The off-budget funds of budget organizations include the development fund of the budget organization, the material incentives and development fund of healthcare organizations, off-budget funds of ministries, state committees, and agencies, as well as off-budget funds formed from the receivables of budget organizations. If we examine the budget organizations funded by the state budget based on their operational characteristics and directions, state educational and healthcare institutions rank high among budget organizations.

In 2022, the expenditures of the state budget (including transfers allocated to state targeted funds) amounted to 280.3 trillion soums, and in 2025, it is expected to reach 362.5 trillion soums, which stimulates economic growth by increasing targeted expenditures for the development of specific sectors. The largest portion of state budget expenditures is attributed to social sector expenditures. (Table 1).

Table 1.

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State budget expenditures by social sectors, trillion som

No	Years	2022	2023	2024	2025
	State budget expenditures	280,3	295,7	312,8	362,5
	in percentage relative to gross domestic product	22,4	23,6	24,0	23,5
1	Social sector expenditures	115,6	130,5	151,4	193,7
	Education	48,6	50,4	69,1	95,1
	Health care	22,1	26,7	33,4	41,3
	Culture	2,3	2,5	2,6	2,8
	Sport	2,4	2,5	2,8	3,1
	Science	1,8	2,0	2,2	2,4

Source. Prepared by the author based on budget information.

Considering the nature of the activities of budget organizations and studying their funding sources, it seems to us that, first of all, it is necessary to pay more attention to the formation of extrabudgetary funds in the social sector, namely in education and healthcare organizations, which have a significant share in the composition of state budget expenditures. This is because by increasing the share of extrabudgetary funds in these organizations, it is possible to slightly reduce the burden on the budget and achieve the development of activities as a result of ensuring material interest based on the requirements of the market economy.

Like previous years, in 2024, the majority of education expenses will also come from the public education system costs (64.3 percent). (Figure 1)

Figure 1. The composition of education expenditures in the state budget for the year 2024. (trillion UZS)

Based on this, it is possible to achieve a slight reduction in the budget burden by increasing the share of extra-budgetary funds in the institutions of the public education system, and by ensuring material interest in accordance with the requirements of the market economy, the development of activities will be attained. Financing the institutions of the public education system from the state budget is considered one of the most important areas of budget expenditures.

In 2022, the total expenditures of the state budget for general secondary education amounted to 33,138.1 billion soums, and by 2025, this figure is projected to reach 54,022.5 billion soums allocated for financing the institutions of the public education system across the republic, which is an increase of 61.3 percent compared to 2022.

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The increase in expenses is also due to the increase in wage amounts as well as the execution of the tasks of the President and Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the expansion of the network of institutions in the public education system and the strengthening of the material and technical base, as well as the allocation of additional funds to pay maternity and childbirth allowances for women working in public education institutions.

If we analyze the composition of the funding sources of institutions in the public education system, we can see that the share of extrabudgetary funds has shown a trend of growth over the last three years (Table 2).

Table 2.

Periodic changes in the share (percentage) of budget and off-budget funds in the financing of public education system institutions.

Organizations in the national education system institutions	2022			2023			2024		
	<i>Funding from the budget</i>	<i>Funding from sources outside the budget</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Funding from the budget</i>	<i>Funding from sources outside the budget</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Funding from the budget</i>	<i>Funding from sources outside the budget</i>	<i>Number</i>
Secondary schools	98,8	1,2	9 959	98,2	1,8	9 972	98,1	1,9	10 072
boarding schools	98,1	1,9	227	97,9	2,1	227	97,7	2,3	227
Houses of Compassion	99,5	0,5	127	98,8	1,2	127	98,6	1,4	127
Presidential schools	99,8	0,2	14	99,5	0,5	14	99,3	0,7	14
"Perfect Generation" Creative and Special Schools		1,3	180		1,7	180		2,1	180

In the educational institutions of the public education system, calculations with buyers and customers will be carried out regarding products developed specifically for the type of activities funded by the development fund, as well as for works performed and services provided. Additionally, calculations will be conducted regarding the leasing of idle fixed assets and the sale of secondary raw materials. These calculations will be formalized based on primary documents and recorded in accounting registers. The most important aspect of accounting for the formation and revenue of extra-budgetary funds in public educational institutions is the systematic documentation of the processes from the recognition of funds as income to their receipt in the accounting, based on these documents.»

Conclusions and recommendations. Based on the specific activities of institutions in the public education system, extra-budgetary funds will be formed. In turn, when managing these extra-budgetary funds, these features will also be taken into account in their accounting, and reports on the movement of extra-budgetary funds will be generated. There are sufficient material and technical

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resources to implement these practices and opportunities for forming extra-budgetary funds in public education institutions.

By wisely utilizing these opportunities, the increase in extra-budgetary funds in public education institutions will lead to a reduction in budget expenditures and, in turn, a decrease in the tax burden.

The observations and analyses above indicate how significant the importance of extra-budgetary funds is, we need to carry out the following activities related to improving the methodology of accounting for external funds:

strictly implement the application of accounting methods in relation to income recognition from the realization of products (work, services) specific to the types of activities in the institutions of the public education system;

the head of the educational institution is responsible for developing an accounting policy to manage the financial and economic activities of the institution, ensuring the effective functioning of the accounting information system, and ensuring accurate accounting of off-budget funds;

ensuring compliance with established standards in the use of financial resources based on the activities of general secondary education institutions, including the state budget, off-budget funds, sponsorship, and other resources.».

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